

APPENDIX A – INVITATION FOR DEVELOPERS AND END USERS PARTICIPATION

DEVELOPERS

Invitation to Evaluate Developer Usability with Blockchain API

Hello, <NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>! How are you?

My name is <RESEARCHER_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW> and I am completing my degree in Computer Science at <UNIVERSITY OMITTED FOR REVIEW>. My final project proposes the integration of SPU systems with blockchain, focusing on **transparency and traceability of public processes**, especially Decentralized Execution Terms (TEDs).

As part of the proposal evaluation, I would like to ask for your help in **validating the developer usability** when interacting with the built blockchain-based API (<API_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>).

Participation consists of:

- A brief test with the API (basic request implementations) using the **Java** programming language.
- A **videoconference** session (about 40 minutes), with observation of the task and use of the **Think-Aloud** technique.
- No prior knowledge of SPU or familiarity with the SEI system is required, only experience with REST API consumption.

If you are interested and available, you can schedule a time at **the link** below, as convenient for you:

After scheduling, we will contact you to confirm and send the videoconference link via **Google Meet**.

Thank you very much in advance for your attention and support!

Best regards,

END USERS

Hello, <NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>! How are you?

My name is <RESEARCHER_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>, and I am completing my degree in Computer Science at <INSTITUTION OMITTED FOR REVIEW>. My final project proposes the integration of <ORGANIZATION

OMITTED FOR REVIEW> systems with blockchain, focusing on transparency and traceability of public processes, especially Decentralized Execution Terms (TEDs).

As part of the evaluation of the proposal, I would like to ask for your collaboration in conducting some usability and user experience tests on the <PROTOTYPE_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW> visual prototype.

Participation consists of:

- A brief test of the prototype (basic interactions with the web page).
- A videoconference session (about 15 minutes), with observation of the task and use of the **Think-Aloud** technique.

If you are interested and available, you can schedule a time at the link below, as convenient for you:

After scheduling, we will contact you to confirm and send you the videoconference link via **Google Meet**.

Thank you very much in advance for your attention and support!

Best regards,